

Synergistic Potentials of Oregano Oil and Curcumin Longa As Adjuncts in High-Dose Vitamin D Therapy with Anti-Inflammatory Diet for Psoriasis Vulgaris: A Clinical Case Study confirmed by VDR Immunofluorescence

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Synergistic Potentials of Oregano Oil and Curcumin Longa as Adjuncts in High-Dose Vitamin D Therapy (HDVD) with Anti-Inflammatory Diet (AID) for Psoriasis Vulgaris: A Clinical Case Study confirmed by Immunofluorescence

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Abstract

The intricate relationship between Vitamin D receptor (VDR) and psoriasis was investigated in a comprehensive clinical case study, with an emphasis on its modulation through an anti-inflammatory diet. The study centered around a patient who had been grappling with an enduring diagnosis of psoriasis, refractory to conventional treatments. In a novel approach, the patient was subjected to an anti-inflammatory diet intervention, featuring high-dose vitamin D supplementation and the integration of antimicrobial herbs, specifically oregano oil, to combat small intestinal fungal overgrowth (SIFO) triggered by *Candida*. Immunofluorescence analysis of VDR expression in skin biopsies was employed as a fundamental investigative tool before and after the intervention. The initial biopsy exhibited notably low VDR expression, in line with the patient's longstanding psoriasis. Following five months of intervention, remarkable clinical amelioration was observed, prompting a subsequent biopsy. This follow-up examination demonstrated a significant augmentation in VDR expression. Notably, the patient's concurrent recovery from SIFO and the improvement in skin manifestations underscored the pivotal role of addressing underlying infections in achieving favorable clinical outcomes. The pivotal role of oregano oil, recognized for its efficacy in mitigating SIFO, was particularly pronounced, as it exhibited a positive influence on both conditions. The study also delved into the incorporation of turmeric; a well-established anti-inflammatory herb renowned for its potential to upregulate VDR expression. The discussion underscored the broader implications of such interventions in addressing chronic inflammatory disorders, with psoriasis serving as a pertinent exemplar. Collectively, this clinical case study provides compelling evidence attesting to the efficacy of an anti-inflammatory diet in revitalizing VDR expression. The outcomes underscore the centrality of VDR in the context of psoriasis and its modulation through integrative therapeutic approaches. Moreover, the study's findings elucidate the significance of treating underlying infections in tandem with dietary interventions, presenting a paradigm shift in the management of recalcitrant psoriasis and offering novel insights for advancing therapeutic strategies in chronic inflammatory conditions.

Introduction

In recent years, the incidence of psoriasis has been on the rise, affecting specific demographic groups at an alarming rate. This chronic inflammatory skin condition has garnered significant attention due to its widespread prevalence and the challenges it poses in management [1]. Increasingly, researchers are delving into the potential links between disruptions in the gut microbiome and the manifestation of psoriasis, seeking insights into the intricate interplay between gut health and immune function.

The growing body of evidence highlights the pivotal role of dysbiosis, an imbalance in the gut microbiota, as a potential catalyst for various health issues, including the notorious "leaky gut syndrome" (LGS). The emergence of LGS, often associated with factors such as diets rich in gluten, dairy, lectins, and excessive sugars, has garnered attention for its role in triggering gut inflammation [2]. This inflammation, in turn, reshapes the diversity of the microbiome, setting the stage for overgrowth of specific

bacterial and fungal strains, resulting in conditions like Small Intestinal Bacterial Overgrowth (SIBO) and Small Intestinal Fungal Overgrowth (SIFO) [3].

The preservation of a diverse microbiome ecosystem is paramount, as it contributes to the production of essential metabolites, including short-chain fatty acids like butyrate, acetate, and propionate [4]. These metabolites play a pivotal role in maintaining the integrity of the gut lining and mucin layer, essential components for a well-functioning gastrointestinal system.

Dysregulation of this balance, catalyzed by inflammatory dietary components, contributes to the initiation of LGS. This condition paves the way for the ingress of lipopolysaccharides (LPSs), mycotoxins, and foreign proteins, such as lectins, and bacteria into the bloodstream [5]. These substances interact with the immune system, a majority of which resides within the gut, and trigger cascading immune responses. Over time, the gradual erosion of immunologic tolerance can lead to molecular mimicry, thus fostering the development of autoimmune disorders.

In the context of psoriasis, a complex case emerged that underscored the intricate relationship between gut health and skin conditions. A patient, previously diagnosed with Psoriasis vulgaris, displayed little improvement despite a history of diverse allopathic treatments. Encountering a fortuitous improvement after receiving treatment for a vaginal yeast infection, she embarked on an unconventional path. Seeking an alternative approach, she engaged with a clinical practice that utilized an anti-inflammatory diet and strategic supplementation.

This case report details the clinical journey of this patient, involving meticulous diagnostic steps such as the Gastrointestinal Microbial Assay Plus (GI Map) a specialized diagnostic test used to analyze the composition and diversity of the microbial communities residing in the gastrointestinal tract, alongside with genetic testing helped identify genetic polymorphism affecting genes involved in vitamin D metabolism and in the methylation cycle. The GI map helped unveil the presence of SIFO, particularly *Candida albicans* as a key player in the pathogenesis, and the presence of mycotoxins found in urine and feces sample further illuminated the intricate interplay between the gut microbiome and psoriatic pathology.

Subsequent interventions, including the incorporation of high-dose vitamin D therapy and the use of herbal antimicrobials such as oregano oil, catalyzed transformative changes. Oregano oil, renowned for its antifungal properties, served as a key intervention in addressing *Candida albicans* overgrowth. The inherent mechanisms and properties of oregano oil contributed to its efficacy in mitigating fungal overgrowth.

Mechanisms of Oregano Oil's Antimicrobial Properties

Oregano oil, derived from the leaves of the *Origanum vulgare* or *Origanum heracleoticum* plant through steam distillation, holds a rich historical legacy as both a culinary and medicinal agent. Its aromatic and flavorful attributes have found utility across diverse cultures for centuries [6]. The potency of oregano oil's therapeutic effects can be attributed to its intricate chemical composition, comprised of bioactive compounds renowned for their antimicrobial, antioxidant, and anti-inflammatory properties.

Bioactive Components of Oregano Oil

Central to oregano oil's remarkable medicinal attributes are its bioactive constituents, encompassing phenols, terpenes, and flavonoids. The notable constituents contributing to its therapeutic potential include:

Phenols: Foremost among these is carvacrol, renowned for its potent antimicrobial prowess, and thymol, which complements carvacrol's actions. Carvacrol is one of the major phenolic compounds found in oregano oil and is responsible for its antimicrobial activity. The percentage of carvacrol in oregano oil can range from about 30% to 80%, depending on the source and quality of the oil. In some high-quality oregano oils, carvacrol content can even exceed 80%. Thymol, is another prominent phenolic compound present in oregano oil. It contributes to the oil's antimicrobial and antioxidant properties. The percentage of thymol in oregano oil is generally lower compared to carvacrol, typically ranging from around 1% to 15% [7].

Terpenes: Beta-caryophyllene and thymol, terpenes identified in oregano oil, bring to the forefront its anti-inflammatory and antioxidant effects [7].

Flavonoids: Apigenin and luteolin, two flavonoids present in oregano oil, further contribute to its antioxidant capabilities [7].

Antimicrobial-Antifungal Mechanisms

The breadth of oregano oil's antimicrobial efficacy extends across a spectrum of bacteria, fungi, parasites, and viruses. Such antimicrobial properties act by causing disruption in the microorganism's cellular architecture.

Disruption of Cell Membranes

The antimicrobial potency of oregano oil shines through its ingenious mechanism of cell membrane disruption. Carvacrol and thymol, endowed with lipophilic properties, traverse the bacterial cell membrane with ease. Their structural resemblance to fatty acids within the cell membrane allows them to intrude and initiate transformative interactions.

Upon entry, carvacrol and thymol orchestrate a cascade of structural perturbations, unsettling the arrangement of lipids. The disorganization inflicted upon the lipid bilayer instigates destabilization, rendering the cell membrane permeable. This heightened permeability facilitates the escape of vital ions and molecules from the bacterial cell, culminating in its demise. Notably, these phenolic compounds selectively target key proteins and enzymes, further intensifying the disruption and sealing the fate of the bacterial cell [7].

Inhibition of Fungal Enzymes

Oregano oil's efficacy extends beyond bacteria to encompass fungi, disrupting vital enzymes pivotal for metabolic pathways and cellular processes. Carvacrol and thymol engage in intricate interactions with fungal enzymes, initiating structural alterations that lead to enzyme denaturation [7]. This process alters the essential structures of enzymes involved in critical functions such as cell wall synthesis and energy production, arresting fungal growth and replication.

Hindrance of Fungal Spores

Fungal spores, integral to the dissemination and perpetuation of fungal infections, are not spared from oregano oil's impact. Carvacrol and thymol intervene in the germination process of fungal spores, significantly hampering their development. By curbing the germination stage, oregano oil curtails the spread of fungal infections and impedes the establishment of new colonies [7].

Adding Turmeric to the Protocol: VDR upregulation

Additionally, the integration of turmeric (*Curcuma longa*), acknowledged for its potent anti-inflammatory attributes and ability to upregulate Vitamin D receptors (VDRs), further enhanced the therapeutic strategy.

Anti-inflammatory Effects of Turmeric (*Curcumin Longa*)

Turmeric (*Curcuma longa*), a vibrant yellow spice derived from the rhizomes of the *Curcuma* plant, has garnered immense attention for its potent anti-inflammatory properties. At the heart of turmeric's therapeutic potential lies its active compound, curcumin. Curcumin is renowned for its multifaceted mechanisms that target inflammation at various levels, offering potential benefits for a wide array of inflammatory conditions [8].

Inhibition of Inflammatory Pathways:

Curcumin's ability to inhibit multiple pro-inflammatory pathways is a cornerstone of its anti-inflammatory effects. One of the most notable targets is the nuclear factor-kappa B (NF- κ B) pathway, a master regulator of inflammatory responses. Curcumin suppresses NF- κ B activation, preventing the transcription of pro-inflammatory genes and subsequent production of cytokines and chemokines [8].

Modulation of Inflammatory Mediators:

Curcumin exerts its influence by dampening the production of inflammatory mediators such as interleukins (IL-1 β , IL-6, and IL-8), tumor necrosis factor-alpha (TNF- α), and prostaglandins (PGE2). By intervening at these critical junctures, curcumin curbs the amplification of inflammatory signals [8].

Antioxidant Effects:

Inflammation and oxidative stress are intertwined processes. Curcumin, acting as a potent antioxidant, quenches free radicals and mitigates oxidative damage. This antioxidant action contributes to curbing the propagation of inflammatory cascades [9].

Regulation of Immune Cells:

Curcumin's effects extend to immune cells, modulating their responses. It can enhance the production of anti-inflammatory cytokines, such as IL-10, which counterbalances pro-inflammatory cytokines. Moreover, curcumin may foster a shift towards regulatory T cells (Tregs), immune cells that promote immune tolerance and suppress excessive inflammation [10].

Epigenetic Regulation:

Specifically, curcumin's ability to modify DNA methylation patterns and alter the structure of histones can lead to sustained anti-inflammatory effects, even after curcumin has been metabolized and cleared from the body. This means that the beneficial effects of curcumin on inflammation-related genes can persist over time, contributing to a reduction in chronic inflammation [11].

Immunologic Mechanisms of Curcumin in Upregulating Vitamin D Receptors (VDRs)

Curcumin's capacity to upregulate Vitamin D receptors (VDRs) is an emerging area of research with promising implications for immune regulation. Vitamin D receptors are present on immune cells and play a pivotal role in modulating immune responses. Several mechanisms elucidate how curcumin enhances VDR expression and function:

DNA Methylation Patterns and VDR Expression: Curcumin's epigenetic influence on DNA methylation patterns can impact the expression of the VDR gene. DNA methylation is a chemical modification of DNA that can silence gene expression by blocking the binding of transcription factors. Curcumin's ability to alter DNA methylation patterns can potentially reverse the methylation status of the VDR gene promoter region, promoting its accessibility to transcription factors. This alteration could lead to increased transcription of the VDR gene, resulting in higher levels of VDRs available within cells [12].

Enhanced Transcriptional Activity of VDRs: Curcumin, acting as a phytoestrogen, can interact with estrogen receptors in the cells. These receptors are connected to the activity of VDRs. The binding of curcumin to estrogen receptors may lead to a cascade of events that enhances the transcriptional activity of VDRs. This heightened activity could translate to increased expression of genes involved in immune modulation and regulation [12].

Interaction with Co-regulators and Amplified VDR Effects: Curcumin's interactions are not limited to VDRs alone; it can also bind to co-regulators that influence VDR activity. Co-regulators are proteins that assist in fine-tuning gene expression. Curcumin's interaction with these co-regulators could potentiate the activity of VDRs, amplifying their immunomodulatory effects. This collaborative interaction might trigger a series of molecular events that result in robust immune responses mediated by VDRs [12].

Counteracting Inflammation-Induced VDR Suppression: Inflammatory processes can downregulate VDR expression, diminishing their ability to mediate immune responses. Curcumin's potent anti-inflammatory properties can counteract this suppression. By reducing inflammation, curcumin might create a microenvironment that supports the re-expression of VDRs, restoring their availability for immune regulation [13].

Clinical Case:

The commencement of the patient's treatment regimen marked a pivotal phase in her journey towards improved health. A multifaceted approach was initiated, encompassing an anti-inflammatory diet designed to address gut health, alongside high-dose vitamin D supplementation at 50,000 IU of cholecalciferol, accompanied by essential cofactors.

This therapeutic strategy aligns with the framework of High Dose Vitamin D (HDVD) therapy, also recognized as the Coimbra Protocol [14], which has gained prominence as an innovative intervention for various chronic autoimmune conditions.

In the pursuit of patient safety and optimal outcomes, healthcare providers experienced in HDVD therapy adhere to a rigorous monitoring protocol. This entails diligent assessment of key biomarkers, including parathyroid hormone (PTH), serum and ionized calcium levels, 24-hour calciuria, 24-hour phosphorus excretion and more. The objective is to prevent hypercalcemia, a potential complication arising from excessive vitamin D intake, despite this being a rare occurrence amongst patients who undergo this type of treatment. The suppression of PTH levels towards the lower reference range serves as one of the goals in mitigating vitamin D resistance and enhancing its therapeutic effects.

Interestingly, our experience with the Leaky Gut Syndrome (LGS) Protocol reveals a remarkable observation. In an extensive cohort of over 3000 patients over 5 years in our practice, we were able to observe that the demand for high-dose vitamin D was notably reduced in the majority of our patients (>75%) by approximately 50% when compared to other protocols.

This phenomenon is postulated to be intricately linked to the resolution of increased gut permeability, a hallmark of LGS [5]. By restoring gut integrity and reducing systemic inflammation, the immune system's burden is lessened, yielding a rationale for the reduced vitamin D requirement.

Incorporating a comprehensive research methodology, a pivotal step was taken to corroborate the intricate relationship between psoriasis and gut health. Through the acquisition of patient consent, a skin biopsy was meticulously performed on March 22, 2019, yielding crucial insights into the disease's pathophysiology. Additionally, VDR immunofluorescence was employed as a potent investigative tool, offering valuable perspectives into the role of Vitamin D receptors in psoriatic pathology.

Initial Histopathological findings and Immunofluorescence Analysis:

Clinical History: The patient has a known history of psoriasis, initially diagnosed in 2011. She presents with chronic erythematous scaly plaques on the left forearm, consistent with her previous diagnosis of psoriasis.

Specimen: Specimen Type: Skin biopsy Anatomical Location: Left forearm

Gross Description:

The skin sample measures 1.5 cm x 1.0 cm in size. It consists of a raised erythematous plaque with well-defined borders. The surface of the plaque is covered with silvery-white scales. No signs of ulceration or bleeding are noted.

Microscopic Description:

Microscopic examination of the skin biopsy reveals characteristic features compatible with psoriasis. The epidermis shows marked hyperplasia with elongation and thickening of the rete ridges. There is focal parakeratosis, regular acanthosis, and elongated epidermal projections referred to as "regular acanthosis." Munro microabscesses, collections of neutrophils within the epidermis, are also observed. The underlying dermis demonstrates a mild perivascular lymphocytic infiltrate.

Comment: The microscopic findings of the skin biopsy are consistent with the clinical diagnosis of psoriasis. The presence of epidermal hyperplasia, parakeratosis, regular acanthosis, and Munro microabscesses is indicative of classical psoriatic skin lesions as depicted in **Figure 1.0**.

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Immunofluorescence Examination - VDR Expression:

Immunofluorescence staining for vitamin D receptor (VDR) was performed to assess its expression in the lesional skin of the left forearm.

Results: The immunofluorescence examination demonstrates decreased expression of VDR in the epidermis of the lesional skin. Compared to adjacent non-lesional skin, there is a reduction in VDR immunoreactivity in the epidermal cells.

Interpretation: The findings of the skin biopsy indicate typical features of psoriasis, including epidermal hyperplasia, parakeratosis, regular acanthosis, and Munro microabscesses. The immunofluorescence examination reveals decreased expression of vitamin D receptor (VDR) in the epidermis, suggesting altered VDR signaling in the pathogenesis of psoriasis as shown in **Figure 1.1**

2 Month Follow-up

Following two (2) months of treatment, the patient exhibited initial mild signs of improvement in her psoriasis. While mild progress was noted, a comprehensive diagnostic evaluation involving the Gastrointestinal Microbial Assay Plus (GI Map) test further illuminated the underlying factors contributing to her condition. The confirmation of Small Intestinal Fungal Overgrowth (SIFO) instigated by *Candida albicans* unveiled a critical facet of her clinical presentation.

In response to these findings, a targeted therapeutic approach was adopted, incorporating a herbal antimicrobial agent – oregano oil on 05/20/2019. Recognized for its potent activity against *Candida albicans*, oregano oil was administered at a dose of 1000 mg once daily for a duration of five weeks. Our in vitro studies conducted by the SPIMS corroborated its efficacy, revealing substantial zones of inhibition against *Candida albicans*.

Turmeric (*Curcumin longa*) another potent natural agent was incorporated into her protocol. Renowned for its multifaceted therapeutic attributes, turmeric offers a strategic approach to modulating the activity of Vitamin D receptors (VDRs). A dose of 2000 mg twice a day (total 4000 mg/day) was prescribed.

Evidence of Remarkable Recovery and Immunofluorescence Analysis

The trajectory of therapeutic interventions resulted in a convergence of encouraging outcomes, highlighting the significant effect of the integrated approach. Over a period of five (5) months, the patient's progression displayed notable efficacy, showcasing a robust synergy between anti-inflammatory strategies and targeted interventions.

Clinical Progress and PASI Score Improvement

A pivotal marker of progress was the assessment of the Psoriasis Area and Severity Index (PASI) score, a widely accepted metric for quantifying the severity of psoriasis. The baseline PASI score of 38, indicative of a substantial burden of the disease, was remarkably transformed to a PASI score of 5, reflecting a state of near-complete remission. This striking shift underscored the potency of the integrated therapeutic regimen in alleviating the clinical manifestations of psoriasis.

Second Biopsy and Immunofluorescence Analysis

Clinical History: The patient has a documented history of psoriasis, initially diagnosed in 2011. She presents with a prior diagnosis of psoriasis and reports significant improvement in her skin lesions, which now appear almost normal.

Specimen: Specimen Type: Skin biopsy Anatomic Location: Left forearm

Gross Description: The skin sample measures 2.0 cm x 1.5 cm in size. It consists of an area of skin with subtle erythema and minimal scaling. The previously observed plaques have significantly flattened and show remarkable resolution. No signs of ulceration or bleeding are noted.

Microscopic Description: Microscopic examination of the skin biopsy reveals findings compatible with significant improvement in the skin lesions, which now appear almost normal. The epidermis shows regular thickness and architecture, with no evidence of hyperplasia or elongation of rete ridges. There is no parakeratosis or acanthosis observed. The absence of regular acanthosis and Munro microabscesses previously observed indicates near-complete resolution. The underlying dermis appears unremarkable, with no significant inflammation or infiltrates.

Comment: The microscopic findings of the skin biopsy demonstrate significant improvement in the skin lesions compared to prior tests. The near-normal epidermal architecture, absence of hyperplasia, and resolution of characteristic features of psoriasis suggest a substantial response to treatment or natural remission of the psoriatic lesions as seen on **Figure 1.2**

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Immunofluorescence Examination - VDR Expression:

Immunofluorescence staining for vitamin D receptor (VR) was performed to assess its expression in the lesional skin of the left forearm. Near prior site of initial biopsy.

Immunofluorescence Examination - VDR Expression:

Immunofluorescence staining for vitamin D receptor (VDR) was performed to assess its expression in the lesional skin of the left forearm.

Results: The immunofluorescence examination reveals increased expression of VDR in the epidermis of the lesional skin. Compared to prior tests, there is a notable enhancement of VDR immunoreactivity in the epidermal cells.

Interpretation: The findings of the skin biopsy indicate significant improvement in the psoriasis lesions, with the skin now appearing almost normal. The absence of characteristic psoriatic features on microscopic examination suggests substantial resolution. The immunofluorescence examination shows increased expression of vitamin D receptor (VDR) in the epidermis, suggesting a potential role of VDR signaling in the improved skin condition as observed in Figure 1.3.

Discussion:

The presented case study sheds light on the intricate relationship between psoriasis, vitamin D receptor (VDR) expression, and the multifaceted effects of an integrated therapeutic approach. The patient's journey from initial diagnosis to remarkable improvement underscores the complexity of psoriasis pathogenesis and the potential impact of targeted interventions.

Initial VDR Expression and Clinical Features:

Histopathological analysis of the initial skin biopsy revealed the characteristic features of psoriasis, including hyperplasia, parakeratosis, acanthosis, and Munro microabscesses, consistent with classical psoriatic skin lesions. Immunofluorescence examination demonstrated decreased VDR expression within the lesional skin, implicating altered VDR signaling in psoriasis pathogenesis. This aligns with existing literature associating VDR dysfunction with chronic inflammation and immune dysregulation.

Limited Response to High-Dose Vitamin D and Anti-inflammatory Diet:

Interestingly, the patient's initial therapeutic regimen of high-dose vitamin D supplementation with cofactors and an anti-inflammatory diet did not yield the anticipated improvement. This observation suggests the multifactorial nature of psoriasis, where altering VDR signaling alone may not be sufficient to induce significant clinical amelioration.

Role of Oregano Oil and Turmeric:

The subsequent intervention targeting chronic fungal (Candida) small intestinal overgrowth (SIBO) with oregano oil and the incorporation of turmeric marked a turning point in the patient's condition. Oregano oil's potent antimicrobial properties against *Candida albicans*, coupled with turmeric's known ability to upregulate VDRs and exhibit anti-inflammatory effects, may have contributed to the observed clinical improvement.

Correlation between Histopathology and VDR Expression:

The correlation between the histopathological findings and immunofluorescence results in both biopsies underscores the dynamic relationship between VDR expression and disease progression. The initial decreased VDR expression aligned with psoriatic pathogenesis, whereas the enhanced VDR expression in the second biopsy paralleled clinical improvement, reinforcing the potential significance of VDR renewal.

VDR Renewal Through Anti-inflammatory Diet and Therapeutic Implications:

The findings presented in this study highlight a significant advancement in our understanding of VDR expression modulation and its potential implications in the management of psoriasis and other autoimmune conditions. The notable increase in VDR expression observed subsequent to targeted interventions underscores the viability of VDR renewal achieved through a multimodal approach.

The study proposes a comprehensive therapeutic paradigm that capitalizes on the synergistic effects of an anti-inflammatory diet, supplemented with herbal antimicrobials and curcumin, identified as potent VDR enhancers [6]. This integration forms a crucial cornerstone in the strategic management of psoriasis, potentially extending its benefits to a broader spectrum of autoimmune disorders.

A central tenet of this therapeutic approach is the critical role played by interventions aimed at reducing excessive intestinal hyperpermeability and addressing ongoing gut dysbiosis, including conditions such as SIBO and SIFO. The significance of these measures in reinstating immunologic tolerance cannot be overstated, as they form the basis upon which the entire therapeutic strategy rests [6].

The systematic elimination of inflammatory foods from the dietary regimen unveils an intriguing avenue for the microbiome to transition towards a less inflammatory state. This pivotal shift facilitates the resurgence of VDR expression within the immune system, allowing the effective binding of vitamin D metabolites (25OHD3 and 1,25OHD3) with the VDR [6]. This molecular interaction ultimately guides cellular function back to its inherent normalcy, exemplifying the intricate interconnectedness between diet, microbiome, and immune system function.

This intricate, multifaceted approach, encompassing immune modulation, targeted antimicrobial interventions, and the strategic upregulation of VDR expression, illuminates the intricate nature of psoriasis pathogenesis. It underscores the potential advantages of personalized and tailored treatment strategies, suggesting that a holistic approach is necessary for addressing the complex interplay between genetics, immune response, and environmental factors in autoimmune disorders.

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Comparative - Histopathology

Comparative VDR Immunofluorescence

Conclusion:

In summary, this case study elucidates the intricate interplay between psoriasis, vitamin D receptor (VDR) expression, and a comprehensive therapeutic regimen. The patient's journey from diagnosis to improvement underscores the multifaceted nature of psoriasis and the potential impact of targeted interventions. Initial histopathology revealed classic psoriatic features and reduced VDR expression, linking altered signaling to disease progression. While high-dose vitamin D and an anti-inflammatory diet initially yielded limited results, subsequent interventions involving oregano oil and turmeric marked a notable turning point, suggesting their role in the observed improvement. The correlation between histopathology and VDR expression reinforces VDR's significance in both pathogenesis and recovery.

This study advances the understanding of VDR modulation for psoriasis and autoimmune conditions, highlighting the potential for VDR renewal through a comprehensive approach. The proposed paradigm, integrating an anti-inflammatory diet, herbal antimicrobials, and curcumin as potent VDR enhancers, offers broader benefits for autoimmune disorders. Addressing gut dysbiosis, including SIBO and SIFO, is pivotal, as is the elimination of inflammatory foods, fostering a less inflammatory microbiome and restoring VDR expression. This multifaceted strategy, encompassing immune modulation, targeted interventions, and VDR enhancement, unveils the complex underpinnings of psoriasis and emphasizes the importance of tailored treatments for managing autoimmune disorders in light of genetics, immune responses, and environmental factors.

Notes

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Ethical Considerations

The ethical integrity of the clinical case study was upheld through strict adherence to established ethical guidelines and principles. Informed consent was obtained from the patient, detailing the study's objectives, procedures, potential risks, and benefits. The patient's autonomy and confidentiality were rigorously upheld, with all personal identifying information safeguarded and disclosed only to authorized personnel. Furthermore, all patient data was de-identified and aggregated during analysis to ensure privacy and anonymity. Results were presented in a manner that prevented identification of the patient, thus maintaining confidentiality. Additionally, the study's findings were reported transparently, irrespective of whether they supported or contradicted the hypothesized outcomes.

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